

Influence of Laser Irradiation on the Photoluminescence Intensity of InGaAsN Quantum Wells

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

We have investigated the influence of laser irradiation on the photoluminescence (PL) intensity of InGaAsN quantum wells (QWs) to emulate the performance degradation during device operation. The PL intensity was reduced with fast and slow components by laser irradiation with higher power densities. For a sample with a high nitrogen concentration of 1.3%, however, it is found that the PL intensity increases with irradiation time at laser power densities lower than ~ 240 kW/cm². The improvement in the PL intensity can be explained by the fact that annihilation of nitrogen-related as-grown defects by laser irradiation. The amount and rate of the PL intensity degradation of InGaAsN QWs with different N and In compositions by laser irradiation are also discussed. Thus, it is demonstrated that real-time PL measurements with high power density excitation are useful to the analysis of degradation processes.

Keywords: DILUTE NITRIDE SEMICONDUCTORS, LASER IRRADIATION, PHOTOLUMINESCENCE (PL), QUANTUM WELL (QW), DEFECTS

1. Introduction

Dilute nitride semiconductors have been attracting considerable attention for their unconventional physical behaviors, such as large band gap bowing (Weyers et al. 1992; Baillargeon et al. 1992; Miyoshi et al. 1993; Kondow et al. 1994; Bi et al. 1996; Yaguchi et al. 1997; Shih et al. 2003) which makes it possible to simultaneously reduce the lattice constant and band gap energy in the lower nitrogen concentration range.

Among dilute nitride semiconductors, InGaAsN is expected to be a promising material for long-wavelength semiconductor lasers with a high characteristic temperature (Kondow et al. 1996; Kitatani et al. 2000; Sato 2000; Riechert et al. 2000; Fischer et al. 2002) because of a large conduction band offset at the heterojunction with GaAs or AlGaAs. InGaAsN is also a candidate material for a 1 eV sub-cell in high-efficiency multijunction solar cells (Friedman et al. 1998; Kurtz et al. 1999; Jackrel et al. 2007) because it can be grown lattice matched to GaAs or Ge. However, the large difference in size between As and N atoms potentially contributes to the formation of defects (Zhang et al. 2001). Lower temperatures required for incorporating N atoms during epitaxial growth of InGaAsN also cause the formation of defects that act as nonradiative recombination centers, and thus post-annealing is often performed to eliminate some defects (Xin et al. 1999; Pan et al. 2000; Li et al. 2001; Xie et al. 2005). In addition to such as-grown defects, the generation or multiplication of defects that acts as nonradiative recombination centers may possibly occur during device operation (Lu et al. 2009). Therefore, it is crucial to investigate not only as-grown defects but also defects induced by the action of devices, which are responsible for the performance degradation or device lifetime.

Previously, the performance degradation of semiconductor laser diode during operation was reported (Ueda 2010). In this study, our aims focus on the performance degradation of InGaAsN quantum wells (QWs) during operation. To obtain this, we have performed real-time measurements of the changes in photoluminescence (PL) intensity of InGaAsN QWs under high power density laser irradiation which mimics device operation. We previously reported that photoexcitation with high power density at low temperatures leads to the annihilation of structural defects and increase in the PL intensity of GaAsN (Yaguchi et al. 2003; 2006; Tanioka et al. 2007), and that a noticeable decrease in the PL intensity occurs in GaPN during laser irradiation at room temperature (Sultan et al. 2020). This paper reports that the PL intensity of InGaAsN QW with a relatively high N concentration increases during laser irradiation with lower power densities while that decreases for higher power density photoexcitation. We also discuss the amount and rate or speed in terms of time constant of the PL intensity degradation obtained from InGaAsN QWs with different N and In compositions by laser irradiation. Thus, we demonstrate that the real-time PL measurements with high excitation power density is very useful to investigate the degradation processes in InGaAsN QWs.

2. Experimental

The samples used in this study were strained InGaAsN/GaAs single QWs on GaAs (001) substrates grown by metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy. Trimethylindium, trimethylgallium, tertiarybutylarsine and dimethylhydrazine were used for the In, Ga, As, and N sources, respectively. The growth temperatures were 470-580 °C. The sample structure consists of a 100 nm thick GaAs buffer layer, a 7 nm thick InGaAsN well and a 200 nm thick GaAs cap layer. Table I lists the nitrogen and indium concentrations, growth temperature, and lattice mismatch between InGaAsN and GaAs of the samples used in this study. Micro-PL measurements were performed in real time at room temperature using a cw diode-pumped solid-state laser ($\lambda=532$ nm) as the

excitation source. The laser spot size was approximately 1 μm . To inspect the change in the PL intensity, each sample was exposed to the laser with power densities ranging from 1 to 912 kW/cm^2 for 500 s. Although the laser power density was considerably high, the increase in temperature is estimated to be at most several K from the shift of the band gap energy of GaAs. Therefore, the heating effect by the laser irradiation can be ignored under the conditions used in this study. A polychromator integrated with optical elements and an InGaAs linear image sensor was used to measure PL spectra from the samples.

TABLE I. Nitrogen and indium concentrations, growth temperature (T), and lattice mismatch to GaAs ($a_0 = 5.65 \text{ \AA}$) of $\text{In}_y\text{Ga}_{1-y}\text{As}_{1-x}\text{N}_x$ QWs used in this study.

Sample	x (%)	y (%)	T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$\Delta a/a_0$ (%)
A	1.3	33	490	2.1
B	0.6	33	520	2.3
C	0.5	25	540	1.8

3. Results

Figures 1(a), (b) and (c) show the time evolution of the PL spectra observed from samples A, B and C, respectively during the laser irradiation with a power density of $183 \text{ kW}/\text{cm}^2$. Samples A and B have the same In but different N concentrations, while samples B and C have nearly the same N but different In concentrations. It is found from Fig. 1(a) that the PL intensity of sample A steeply increases with laser irradiation time. As can be seen from this figure, the improvement of PL intensity is about 30% from the initial value in 50 s, and becomes more than 40% after 200 s laser irradiation. In contrast, it is found from Fig. 1(b) that the PL intensity of sample B gradually decreases to less than 95% of the initial value in 50 s and reaches about 93% after 200 s irradiation. As can be seen in Fig. 1(c), sample C shows the similar tendency of PL degradation like sample B but the PL degradation is larger and more rapid. Thus, the PL intensity for the sample with a higher N concentration increases while that for lower N concentrations decreases during laser irradiation with a power density of $183 \text{ kW}/\text{cm}^2$. It should be noted that several dips seen in the PL spectra in Fig. 1(a) are attributed to the absorption by optical components used in the micro-PL measurement system.

Figures 2(a), (b) and (c) show the irradiation time dependence of the integrated PL intensity of samples A, B and C, respectively, normalized by the initial value under the laser irradiation with various power densities. As can be seen from Fig. 2(a), it is interesting that the PL intensity increases with laser irradiation time at lower laser power densities while the PL intensity decreases at higher laser power densities.

FIG. 1. Time evolution of PL spectra obtained from (a) sample A ($x=1.3\%$, $y=33\%$), (b) sample B ($x=0.6\%$, $y=33\%$), and (c) sample C ($x=0.5\%$, $y=25\%$) respectively under laser irradiation with a power density of 183 kW/cm^2 .

FIG. 2. Irradiation time dependence of the PL intensity of (a) sample A ($x = 1.3\%$, $y = 33\%$), (b) sample B ($x = 0.6\%$, $y = 33\%$), and (c) sample C ($x = 0.5\%$, $y = 25\%$), respectively for various laser power densities.

In contrast, it is found from Fig. 2(b) that the PL intensity of sample B decreases with laser irradiation time at

any laser power density and more rapidly with increasing laser power density. Similar tendency was also observed for the sample C, though the degradation of the PL intensity was more noticeable, as shown in Fig. 2(c).

The black curves shown in Figs. 2(a)-(c) were obtained by fitting to the following function with fast and slow components,

$$\frac{I(t)}{I(0)} = 1 + A_{\text{fast}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{\text{fast}}}} \right) + A_{\text{slow}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_{\text{slow}}}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where A_{fast} and A_{slow} represent the fast and slow components in normalized integrated PL intensity change, respectively, which can be either positive or negative for the increase or decrease in the PL intensity. τ_{fast} and τ_{slow} are the corresponding time constants. It is found that the PL intensity changes by laser irradiation are well fitted to Eq. (1) despite the phenomenological equation. We found from the fitting to the decrease in the PL intensity of all the samples that A_{fast} and A_{slow} were comparable in magnitude to each other. In addition, as explained below, time constants for the slow component are about an order of magnitude, that is significant, greater than those for the fast component. This clearly indicates there are two kinds of mechanism for the changes in the PL intensity like rapid and gradual degradation modes reported for semiconductor optical devices (Jiménez 2003; Ueda 2010) though the origins may not necessarily be the same.

The limit value $I(\infty)/I(0)$ can be derived from $1 + A_{\text{fast}} + A_{\text{slow}}$ using Eq. (1), and is shown in Fig. 3 as a function of laser power density for samples A, B and C. The corresponding τ_{fast} and τ_{slow} are plotted in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), respectively, as a function of laser power density. The PL intensity always decreased in the whole range measured in this study for samples B and C. The limit value $I(\infty)/I(0)$ has a tendency to decrease as shown in Fig. 3 while the corresponding τ_{fast} and τ_{slow} become shorter, as can be seen from Fig. 4(a) and 4(b), respectively, with increasing laser power density. $I(\infty)/I(0)$ is larger while the corresponding τ_{fast} and τ_{slow} are also larger for sample B in comparison with those parameters of sample C at any laser power density.

In contrast to samples B and C, as can be seen from Fig. 3, the PL intensity of sample A was enhanced in the lower laser power density range, whereas that was reduced in the higher range. In particular, $I(\infty)/I(0)$ is increased by approximately two times after irradiation at laser power density 76 kW/cm^2 . The improvement in the PL intensity has a tendency to become smaller with increasing laser power density, and changes into the degradation by laser irradiation with power density above $\sim 240 \text{ kW/cm}^2$. The parameters $I(\infty)/I(0)$, τ_{fast} and τ_{slow} of normalized PL degradation of sample A have the similar tendency as sample B and C for the PL degradation at laser power densities higher than $\sim 240 \text{ kW/cm}^2$.

FIG. 3. $I(\infty)/I(0)$ as a function of laser power density for samples A, B and C.

FIG. 4. Laser power density dependence of (a) τ_{fast} and (b) τ_{slow} for samples A, B and C.

4. Discussion

4.1 Increase in the PL intensity of sample A by laser irradiation

For sample A, as the laser power density increases, the improvement in the PL intensity becomes smaller and finally changes to the degradation at the laser power density of $\sim 240 \text{ kW/cm}^2$. Despite the difference between photon and electron, Sailai *et al.* (Sailai et al. 2020) reported a similar experimental result that lower electron doses improved PL intensity of InGaAsN/GaAs QW while the PL intensity was degraded at higher electron doses for the changes in the PL intensity before and after the electron irradiation on InGaAsN QW, and proposed recombination-enhanced defect reaction model as a possible explanation, but they did not assign what the defects related to the improvement were. Several kinds of defects, such as N interstitials (Li et al. 2001), Ga vacancies (Toivonen et al. 2003), As_{Ga} antisites (Chen et al. 2006) and Ga interstitials (Wang et al. 2009) have been attributed to as-grown nonradiative defects in (In)GaAsN. Since the N concentration in sample A is higher than that in samples B and C, it is suggested that nitrogen atoms should be associated with the enhancement of the PL intensity by the laser irradiation with lower power densities observed only for sample A. This is consistent with our previous report that photo-induced improvement in the PL intensity of GaAsN alloys increased superlinearly with increasing N concentration (Yaguchi et al. 2003). Several papers (Xin et al. 1999; Palmer et al. 2005) reported that with increasing nitrogen concentration in InGaAsN QW, the density of nonradiative recombination centers becomes higher. Therefore, the increase in the PL intensity by laser irradiation for sample A is presumably attributed to the annihilation of higher density N-related as-grown defects acting as nonradiative recombination centers. In contrast, the enhancement of the PL intensity by the laser irradiation was not observed for samples B and C in which the nitrogen concentrations are 0.6% and 0.5%, respectively, and less than half of that in sample A. This result suggests that samples B and C contain little N-related as-grown nonradiative recombination centers which can be annihilated by laser irradiation or that larger degradation of PL intensity due to the formation of some new nonradiative defects overtakes slight improvement in the PL intensity.

Nuclear reaction analysis with Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (Li et al. 2001) revealed that N interstitials decreased in GaAsN after annealing at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Considering the similarity between the effects of anneal and laser irradiation on the annihilation of nonradiative recombination centers in terms of excited-state dynamics and the PL improvement observed for only the sample with a higher N concentration in this study, N interstitials are candidates for the as-grown defects which can be removed by laser irradiation. Laaksonen *et al.* (Laaksonen et al. 2008) found from the total energy calculations based on density-functional theory that the lowest energy interstitial-type defects are N-N and N-As split interstitials, which are possibly responsible for nonradiative centers annihilated by laser irradiation in this study.

4.2 Decrease in the PL intensity by laser irradiation

As shown in Fig. 3, the normalized PL intensity of sample B decreased less significantly by laser irradiation in comparison with sample C. Since sample B has nearly the same N but higher In concentrations than sample C, the lattice mismatch of sample B to GaAs is larger than that of sample C as listed in Table I. In addition, sample B was grown at a lower temperature. It is expected from the larger lattice mismatch and lower growth temperature, therefore, that sample B contained a higher density of as-grown nonradiative recombination centers, such as misfit dislocations and point defects than sample C. This is consistent with the fact that the PL from sample B was hardly observed below $\sim 4.5 \text{ kW/cm}^2$ while the PL from sample C could be observed at lower power densities as shown in Fig. 3. Since quite a few nonradiative recombination centers had already existed in sample B, therefore, the degradation of the PL intensity by laser irradiation seems to be less noticeable. Given the fact that larger lattice mismatch and higher In composition led to less degradation, misfit dislocations or In-related defects are possible candidates for as-grown nonradiative defects, though it should be examined by some other experiments. As for new nonradiative defects induced by laser irradiation, misfit dislocations, point defect clusters, and micro-dislocation loops, or point defects as their precursors are probably responsible for the degradation of the PL intensity, as discussed in the following subsection.

4.3 Fast and slow components of the PL intensity degradation by laser irradiation

As explained before, the degradation of the PL intensity by laser irradiation was found to have fast and slow components like rapid and gradual degradation modes observed in semiconductor optical devices (Jiménez 2003; Ueda 2010). Rapid degradation of laser diodes is attributed to recombination-enhanced dislocation climb or recombination-enhanced dislocation glide as a consequence of the interaction between dislocations and point defects enhanced by nonradiative recombination of injected carriers, and gradual degradation is due to the formation of point defect clusters or micro-dislocation loops caused by nonradiative recombination at existing point defects. Although the degradation of the PL intensity observed in this study shows a different time scale from the degradation of laser diodes, it seems to be in a similar situation that nonradiative recombination at existing defects enhances dislocation motion or the formation of new point defects. As shown in Figures 3 and 4, the PL intensity degraded faster and more significantly with increasing laser power density probably because photoexcited carriers, and thus nonradiative recombination increased to enhance the formation of new nonradiative defects. Unlike laser irradiation, it is difficult for electron, proton, or γ -ray irradiation to measure the degradation in real time. Thus, real-time PL measurements with high power density excitation emulates the operation of laser diodes, and gives useful information about the degradation mechanism, such as the degradation rate.

5. Conclusion

We performed real-time measurements of the changes in the PL intensity of InGaAsN QWs with different N and In compositions under laser irradiation which mimics device operation. The PL intensity was found to

decrease with fast and slow components by laser irradiation with higher power densities like rapid and gradual degradation modes of laser diodes. For the sample with a high N concentration of 1.3%, however, the PL intensity increased at laser power densities lower than $\sim 240 \text{ kW/cm}^2$. The improvement in the PL intensity can be explained by the annihilation of N-related as-grown defects acting as nonradiative recombination centers. If quite a few nonradiative recombination centers had already existed, it seems that the PL intensity degraded less noticeably by laser irradiation. Thus, it was demonstrated that real-time PL measurements with high power density laser irradiation provide beneficial information to the analysis of degradation processes in optoelectronic devices during operation.

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